

Development of Recycled Fabric using Different Blend Ratio and their Comfort Properties Analysis

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Abstract:

More businesses are increasingly embracing the idea of supply chain to boost their total profitability as a response to the shortening product life cycles and to remain competitive by managing the business effectively. The rate of returns and their disposals has increased due to the popularity of e-commerce, quicker technological advancements, a shorter life cycle, and increased customer interest in and preference for what is in style. In this research study, in comparison to polyester-cotton and polyester-wool blended fabrics, recycled polyester blended fabrics have slightly reduced air permeability since they are hairier. In comparison to polyester-cotton and polyester-wool blended fabrics, recycled polyester blended fabrics have a higher water vapour permeability and vertical wicking due to microstructure and moisture recovery. When the fabric's GSM increases from the 126 to 138 gram range, its feel factor value decreases as a result of an increase in frictional qualities brought on by the GSM increase. The recycled polyester blend also contributes to an increase in the fabric feel factor and hairiness level. But there is a trend of slightly altering recycled cloth that is all-blend. In comparison to the comparably soft polyester/wool/recycled polyester blend textiles, polyester/cotton/recycled polyester blend fabrics have a soft feel (excellent fabric feel factor). Nearly identical knitted fabrics are available that use recycled polyester fibres. When we used P70C30R00 and P70W30R00 mixed yarn and fabrics, we discovered that up to 7% to 14% recycled polyester fibre was slightly different. Recycled polyester has positive effects on the environment and the economy.

Keywords: *Fabric feel factor, Knit Fabric, Recycled polyester, vertical wicking, Water vapour permeability*

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1. Introduction

More businesses are now embracing the idea of supply chains to boost their overall profitability and ecological advantages in response to growing competition, shortened product life cycles, and effective business management. Product returns and disposals have risen as a result of reduced life cycle. Businesses have come to realize how much value they can recover by recycling or remanufacturing returned or discarded goods. The reverse supply chain is an instrument to simplify and optimize this process of gathering used products, refurbishing them, and then selling them. This academic study aims to list the primary problems associated with creating the reverse chain and the cost concentrations for doing so. The reverse chain and the conventional forward chain are contrasted to show their differences. The conventional forward supply chain manufactures materials, components, and finished goods. Consumers use or consume end items. In addition to the forward flow of items, most businesses also have reverse flows of products that are either actively taken back by the business or actively returned by consumers, frequently for reuse or resale. The reverse supply chain (RSC) of the company is the collection of systems that manage these reverse flows and is the central idea of this study. When it comes to disposal, waste reduction has already grown to be a significant issue for human society. Recycling products or materials appears inevitable to displace the typical one-way

economy, and customers now demand that businesses take steps to minimise their negative effects on the environment throughout the entire production process. Companies were aware of the need to integrate environmental concerns with their expanding economic understanding. Global fiber production increased once more to a record 113 million tonnes in 2021, following a little decline in output caused by COVID-19 in 2020. From 58 million tonnes in 2000 to 113 million tonnes in 2021, the production of fibre on a global scale has nearly doubled during the last two decades. If current trends continue, this production will reach 149 million tons in 2030. The percentage of recycled fibres increased slightly from 8.4% in 2020 to 8.9% in 2021, according to the non-profit Textile Exchange's Preferred Fibre & Materials Market Report, mostly because of a rise in polyester fibre generated from recycled bottles. Nevertheless, less than 1% of the global fibre market in 2021 was made up of recycled pre- and post-consumer textiles. The production of synthetic materials produced from fossil fuels increased from 60 million tonnes in 2020 to 63 million tonnes in 2021. Global sales of recycled textiles are anticipated to reach \$7.6 billion by 2027, up from an estimated \$5.6 billion in 2019. According to the report Global Textile Recycling industry 2021 to 2026, the industry is projected to grow at a CAGR of 3.6% from 2020 to 2027. Utilizing a variety of methods, used clothing and waste fibres are recycled and recovered to generate recycled textile. Municipal garbage, which includes things like used or abandoned clothing, tyres, shoes, carpets, furniture, and non-durable items like sheets and towels, contains the majority of

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recyclable textiles. Recycling textiles reduces demand for virgin resources like wool and cotton as well as pollution, water use, and energy use. The second most polluting industry in the world, behind oil, is the textile and clothing (T&C) sector. It generates more than \$450 billion in yearly sales and employs an estimated 60 million people worldwide. Despite the wide range of products offered, 60% of the T&C market is made up of clothing. Fast fashion is defined as readily available and low-cost clothing. Globally, there will be an apparent consumption of 168.4 billion pieces of clothing in 2021. The Statista Consumer Market Outlook predicts that its value will rise over the next few years, reaching 197.3 billion pieces in 2026. Clothing sales are predicted to quadruple from their current level by 2050. Numerous non-renewable resources are needed and consumed in the manufacture, supply, and use of textile products. The usage of energy, water, and dangerous substances, as well as the production of solid waste and carbon dioxide emissions, are among the environmental issues. Various garment producers claim that businesses are becoming more worried about the forward supply chain for clothing.

2. Material and Methods

2.1. Material

The different aspects of textile material have been considered in the present study. Four types of fibers i.e., Recycled polyester, Virgin Polyester, Cotton and wool are used to prepare the blended fabric samples.

Table 1 - Specification of fibers

Fiber	Length (mm)	Fineness
Recycled polyester	38	1.5 D
Fresh Polyester	38	1.6 D
Wool	38	1.6 D
Cotton	32(Avg. effective)	3.8 mic

From above blended yarns, six different fabric samples, using same yarn count 22 Ne and different blend on Knit fabric produced by circular knitting machine with interlock structure.

Figure 1 - (a) Polyester/Cotton/ Recycle Polyester (b) Polyester/Wool/ Recycle Polyester (70/30/00 blend ratio)

Figure 2 - (a) Polyester/Cotton/ Recycle Polyester (b) Polyester/Wool/ Recycle Polyester (67/30/07 blend ratio)

Figure 3 - (a) Polyester/Cotton/ Recycle Polyester (b) Polyester/Wool/ Recycle Polyester (56/30/14 blend ratio)

2.2. Methods

All-recycled fabrics were preconditioned for 24 hours before testing under typical atmospheric conditions of 65+/-2% RH and 27+/-2oC temperature. The air permeability test, vertical wicking, water vapour permeability tester, and drying rate tester were used to examine the comfort properties.

2.2.1. Fabric particulars

The fabric details measured were: wales per inch (WPI), course per inch (CPI), linear density of yarn (denier), fabric mass per unit area (g/m2) and fabric thickness (mm). The WPI and CPI were measured according to the ASTM D-3887 Standard. Yarn linear density and fabric mass per unit area were measured according to ASTM D 1059- 01 and ASTM D 3776M -09a standard respectively by using an electronic weighing balance.

2.2.2. Thickness testing

Thickness testing was carried out as per BS EN ISO 9073-2: 1995 using the electronic thickness tester at 0.25 KPa pressure. For each sample 30 readings were taken to get the result at 95% confidence level.

2.2.3. Air permeability testing

The construction properties of the yarns and textiles, in which huge volumes are occupied by air, have a direct bearing on a fabric's air permeability. The volume of air travelled through 100 square millimetres of fabric in one second at a pressure difference of 10 millimetres of water is the definition of a fabric's air permeability, which measures how well it permits the passage of air through it. The FX 3300 air permeability tester was used to measure air permeability in accordance with ASTM D737-04. At a test pressure of 98 Pa, testing was conducted inside a 15.07-inch-diameter circular test head. The amount of air passing through the fabric per second was measured in cm3/cm2/s.

2.2.4. Water vapour permeability testing

To determine how resistant textiles and textile composites (particularly active wear fabrics) are to water vapour penetration, the testing standard BS 3424 is used. A water vapour permeability tester was used for this, which contains eight containers with water reservoirs, a typical permeable fabric cover, a sample holder ring, and a precision driving mechanism.

The fabric's water vapour permeability (WVP) was calculated in grammes per square meter per day using equation (I).

$$WVP = \frac{24M}{A_t} g/m^2/day \dots (i)$$

Where,

M = Loss of water (g) through fabric, A = Internal area of the fabric (m2)

t = Time of testing (24 hours)

2.2.5. Vertical wicking

Fabric wicking was assessed using the strip test method, with

the results expressed as wicking height in centimeters. In this experiment, a cloth strip was suspended vertically, its lower edge resting in a container filled with distilled water. Then, the rate at which water rose through the leading edge was observed. A dye was applied to water in order to identify the location of the waterline. The test fabric's ability to wick moisture was determined by measuring the height of rise over time. The fabric's vertical wicking test was conducted in accordance with DIN 53924 standard using a sample size of 20 cm 2.5 cm. On these fabric structures, measurements with periods of 5, 10 and so forth were established with an eye towards wales.

2.2.6. Fabric Feel Factor or (Soft and Harsh feel test)

Only a few tools, such as the Fabric feel tester and the Kawabata evaluation method for fabrics, are now available for objectively assessing fabric handle. A fabric feel tester (Figure 3.10) was utilised to obtain an impartial assessment of the fabric's feel for this investigation.

The test uses a sample that has a 24 cm diameter. Equation (i) was used to determine the fabric feel factor for the fabrics submitted to the test. When the feel factor value is low, the fabric will be softer; however, when it is high, the opposite will be true, making the cloth harsher.

$$Feel\ factor\ (f) = 26.58 + 20.65 * P_E - 0.436 * WE - 0.131 * A + 5.064 * P_R - 0.361 * DR(i)$$

Where,

PE- Peak Height of Extraction curve (Kg)

WE- Area under the curve for extraction curve (Kgmm)

A -Unload fabric across orifice for extraction curve

PR -Peak height for radial curve (kg)

DR-Peak distance for radial curve (mm)

3. Result and Discussions

Table 2 - Knit fabric basic characteristics

Types of Knit fabric	WPI	CPI	Stitch density	Loop Length (mm)	Thic kness (mm)	GSM
P/C/RP (70/30/00)	28.12	19.22	540.46	2.9	0.37	128
P/C/RP (63/30/07)	28.14	19.35	544.50	2.9	0.37	130
P/C/RP (56/30/14)	30.66	20.85	639.26	2.8	0.38	135
P/W/RP (70/30/00)	28.14	19.24	541.42	2.9	0.37	128
P/W/RP (63/30/07)	28.15	19.38	545.54	2.9	0.37	130
P/W/RP (56/30/014)	31.04	20.86	645.34	2.8	0.38	135

Table 3 - Air permeability and Water vapour permeability results

Types of knit fabric	Air Permeability (cm ³ /cm ² .sec)	Water Vapour Permeability (gm/m ² /day)
P/C/RP (70/30/00)	585	1537 ± 22
P/C/RP (63/30/07)	574	1558 ± 18
P/C/RP (56/30/14)	562	1586 ± 13
P/W/RP (70/30/00)	572	1476 ± 13
P/W/RP (63/30/07)	564	1484 ± 12
P/W/RP (56/30/014)	543	1508 ± 08

Table 4 - Vertical wicking test and fabric feel factor value results

Types of knit fabric	Vertical wicking(cm) (Wale wise)	Vertical wicking(cm) (Coarse wise)	Fabric feel factor value (%)
P/C/RP (70/30/00)	7.83	6.21	32.67
P/C/RP (63/30/07)	8.26	6.45	35.08
P/C/RP (56/30/14)	8.73	6.67	39.55
P/W/RP (70/30/00)	5.11	4.52	34.76
P/W/RP (63/30/07)	5.42	4.74	38.27
P/W/RP (56/30/014)	5.76	5.34	42.05

3.1 Water Vapour Permeability

The micro porosity structure and moisture recovery of the fibres affect the fabrics' water vapour permeability. The fabric's ability to absorb moisture will rise if the recycled polyester content is slightly increased, leading to greater diffusion.

Tables 2 & 3 and Figure 4 demonstrate the differences in fabric water vapour permeability with polyester, cotton, recycled polyester, and wool blend factors. The microstructure and moisture recovery are the key factors that influence an increase in water vapour permeability. When compared to polyester fibres, recycled polyester regains moisture a little bit more. Increased water vapour permeability P56C30R14 in comparison to P70C30R00 was discovered on the fabric's surface as a result. Increased water vapour permeability results from an increase in recycled polyester content. Additionally, it saw an increase in the amount of recycled polyester fibre in blends of polyester, cotton, and recycled polyester as well as an improvement in the fabric's water permeability. As a result, the observed rise in recycled polyester fibre content in blends of polyester, wool, and recycled polyester causes an increase in the

Figure 4 - Water Vapour Permeability of recycled polyester with different blend ratio fibres

materials' water vapour permeability. P56W30R14 blended fabrics, for example, are more permeable to water vapour than P70W30R00 blended fabrics.

3.2 Air permeability

Tables 2&3 and Figure 5 demonstrate the differences in fabric air permeability with polyester, cotton, recycled polyester, and wool blend factors. The main cause of the reduced air permeability is the fabric's surface, which is somewhat more hairy in P56C30R14 than P70C30R00. Air permeability decreases as recycled polyester content increases. Additionally, it has been noted that when recycled polyester fibre content in mixes of polyester, cotton, and recycled polyester increases, the fabric's air permeability decreases. In comparison to polyester, recycled polyester has a little bit more hairiness. Thus, it can be shown that the amount of recycled polyester fibre in mixes of polyester, wool, and recycled polyester increases or decreases air permeability. P56W30R14 blended fabrics, compared to P70W30R00 blended fabrics, have less air permeability.

Figure 5 - Air Permeability of recycled polyester with different blend ratio fibres

3.3 Vertical wicking performance

Tables 2 and 4 show the effects of blend and fabric type on the vertical wicking of the fabrics (wale- and course-wise).

According to Figure 6, the P56C30R14 blended textiles have a higher wicking rate in the wale-wise wicking direction than the P70C30R00 mixed fabrics. Additionally, it was noted that the influence of the recycled polyester fibre in mixes of polyester, cotton, and recycled polyester increased the vertical wicking of the fabric. P56C30R14 mixed fabric has greater wicking along the wale than along the course. This is because stronger capillary action in the wale wise direction makes the transfer of water simpler in that direction. Because recycled polyester fibres retain their ability to absorb water, wicking increases as recycled polyester content does. With P70C30R00 & P70W30R00 blended knitted fabric, we discover that up to 7% recycled polyester is slightly different. Additionally, P56W30R14 blended fabrics have a higher wicking direction in both the wale wise and coarse wise directions than P70W30R00 blended fabrics.

Figure 6 - Vertical wicking performance of recycled polyester with different blend ratio fibres

3.4 Fabric feel factor value (%)

Knit materials are utilised for recycled polyester with various blends of cotton and wool for clothing, as can be seen in tables 2 to 4 and Figure 7. P/C/RP 70/30/00, P/C/RP 63/30/07, P/C/RP 56/30/14, P/W/RP 70/30/00, P/W/RP 63/30/07, and P/W/RP 56/30/14 blend garment wear are some examples of these materials. To put it another way, Tables 2 and 4 show that when the fabric's GSM increases from the 128 to 135 gramme range, its feel factor value decreases as a result of an increase in frictional qualities brought on by the GSM increase. The recycled polyester blend also contributes to an increase in the fabric feel factor and hairiness level. But there is a trend of slightly altering recycled cloth that is all-blend. Figure shows that the fabric feels factor value of the P56C30R14 blended textiles is higher than that of the P70C30R00 mixed fabrics. Additionally, it was observed that the presence of some hairiness in recycled fabric raised the fabric feel factor value when recycled polyester fibre was added to blends of polyester, cotton, and recycled polyester. Blended textiles

P56W30R14 to P70W30R00 showed comparable patterns. In comparison to the comparably soft polyester / wool / recycled polyester blend textiles, polyester/cotton/recycled polyester blend fabrics have a soft feel (excellent fabric feel factor)

Figure 7 - Fabric feel factor value of recycled polyester with different blend ratio fibres

4. Conclusions

In this study, we looked at how ecological factors affected how effective the reverse supply chain was in the recycled fabric fashion sector. Then, after creating recycled polyester fibre with added natural fibre to create sustainable fashion wear products and lower the cost of the products, we assessed the comfort performance of the finished knit garment fabric to come to the conclusions that are presented below.

- In comparison to polyester-cotton and polyester-wool blended fabrics, recycled polyester blended fabrics have slightly reduced air permeability since they are hairier.
- In comparison to polyester-cotton and polyester-wool blended fabrics, recycled polyester blended fabrics have a higher water vapour permeability and vertical wicking, due to microstructure and moisture recovery.
- When the fabric's GSM increases from the 126 to 138 gramme range, its feel factor value decreases as a result of an increase in frictional qualities brought on by the GSM increase. The recycled polyester blend also contributes to an increase in the fabric feel factor and hairiness level. But there is a trend of slightly altering recycled cloth that is all-blend. In comparison to the comparably soft polyester/wool/recycled polyester blend textiles, polyester/cotton/recycled polyester blend fabrics have a soft feel (excellent fabric feel factor).
- Nearly identical knitted fabrics are available that use recycled polyester fibres. When we used P70C30R00 and P70W30R00 mixed yarn and fabrics, we discovered that up to 7% to 14% recycled polyester fibre was slightly different. Recycled polyester has positive effects on the environment and the economy.

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